

DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES IN STUDENTS BASED ON DIFFERENTIAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In the article, it is explained that the development of physical qualities of students in technical higher education institutions on the basis of differentiated education is a socio-pedagogical necessity.*

Keywords: *education, differentiation, technique, higher education, institution, physical culture, physical quality, student, development, differentiated education.*

РАЗВИТИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ КАЧЕСТВ СТУДЕНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье поясняется, что развитие физических качеств студентов технических вузов на основе дифференцированного обучения является социально-педагогической необходимостью.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, дифференциация, методика, высшее образование, вуз, физическая культура, физическое качество, студент, развитие, дифференцированное обучение.*

Comprehensive reforms implemented in our country have been the highest goal of the individual society - aimed at finding a solution to the problem of educating a physically and morally mature, mentally mature, spiritually rich person. The modern social processes taking place in our republic have further increased the nation's need for high spiritual potential.

No. PF-5924 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 "On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan", October 30, 2020 "On measures to promote a healthy lifestyle and develop mass sports" Decree No. PF-6099, Resolution No. PQ-4877 of November 03, 2020 "On measures to improve the personnel training system and increase scientific potential in the field of physical education and sports" and the Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 04, 2015 "Physical education and sports "On Amendments and Amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On creation of all conditions for the involvement of students in physical education and sports training in decisions O'RQ-394 and other regulatory legal documents related to the field; in them, special attention is paid to the formation of physical education and sports skills, taking into account their individual abilities and health status. Also, in our society, there are ample opportunities to engage in mass sports, to make a healthy lifestyle into our daily life, to create conditions for physical education and mass sports in higher education institutions and other organizations. At the same time, implementation of specific programs that help to strengthen the health of the population in the field of physical education and sports, wide involvement of young people in sports; "Introduction of innovative forms and methods to the selection (selection) process of talented athletes is defined as an important task.

One of the main tasks of modernizing the system of physical education and sports in modern conditions is to introduce advanced pedagogical technologies into the educational process, taking into account the individual characteristics of students. In recent years, there has

been a tendency to decrease the level of health and physical fitness of students of higher education institutions that are not adapted to the field of sports. Therefore, the problem of differentiated use of tools and methods in physical education and sports is particularly relevant today

At the core of educational research in the developed countries, the USA, Germany, France, China, Japan, and the Russian Federation, much attention is being paid to the study of individual and group differences between educational subjects and thus to their comprehensive physical training in order to optimize the education and upbringing processes based on a differential approach.

The factor of training highly qualified specialists capable of creating new technologies and scientific developments is **differential** (differentiated) education. In the conditions of changing the educational system, the humanization of the education and training process is important. However, this is possible only on the basis of a comprehensively developed and sociologically based methodology of scientific knowledge in the field of education. It should be based on concepts that reflect the true laws of society and individual development.

In technical higher education institutions, physical and intellectual maturity of students through physical education, physical development and physical training, improvement of their abilities and movement activity, formation of healthy lifestyle skills, formation of a set of values, norms and knowledge created and used by society for the purpose of social adaptation is among the issues of special relevance. In this case, it is important to organize the educational process based on a differential approach to the development of students' physical capabilities in the field of physical education and sports.

The directive documents developed by our President and Government indicate the main directions of reforming the physical education and sports system, that is, "to increase the total number of people regularly engaged in physical education and sports to 30%, and the total number of young people participating in sports organizations and institutions to 20%; gradually increasing the quality of trainers and specialists in state sports educational institutions, in particular, the number of employees with higher education to 80%; development and implementation of an effective and transparent system of selection of talented athletes among young people" and others. Therefore, during the development of the physical qualities of future specialists in technical higher education institutions, that is, today's students, on the basis of differential methods, to create conditions for the protection and strengthening of their health, the development of amateur physical education and sports, sports events, mass sports and physical education and health organization of events is of special importance.

Differentiation (lat.: "differentia"- "different", "different")- consideration of individual qualities and abilities of a person, classification.

One of the main tasks of modernizing the physical education and sports system in modern conditions is the problem of differentiated application of pedagogical tools and methods, taking into account the individual characteristics of students. However, the fact that there is an increasing demand for the development of physical qualities of students in technical higher education institutions and the need for scientific justification of the socio-pedagogical necessity of this issue is determined by the following:

1) in recent years, in the rapidly changing lifestyle, the dynamic movement of young people decreases, physical activity is reduced, as a result of which, excess fat accumulates in

tissues and organs, and the appearance of diseases manifested by body weight exceeding the norm by 20 percent or more;

2) diseases that develop against the background of gland disorders in the body as a result of hypothalamus and endocrine obesity, which develop due to high-calorie foods, consumption of sugary and alcoholic beverages, sleep disorders (less or excessive sleep), long sitting in front of the computer and lack of physical activity;

3) observation of cases of chronic difficulties in mastering the educational load in physical culture classes for an "average" physically trained student, as a result of which young people with immature physical qualities do not seek to further improve them and their interest in physical education classes fades.

4) the problem of a differential approach to education attracts the attention of physical culture teachers, sports coaches and specialists, and the need to organize the differential use of various tools and methods in physical culture training, etc. All this shows that the differential approach in pedagogy and psychology is considered as a method of studying individual and group differences between educational subjects in order to optimize the processes of education and upbringing. Therefore, in the development of the physical qualities of students in higher educational institutions, the technique requires an individual approach to the subject himself, to the personal activity of the subject himself, to justify the methods of mastering the educational material, the choice of tools (technological operations), the methods of managing educational activities (teacher activities) in accordance with the purpose of the training.

Differentiated education is a type of education organized taking into account typological differences, showing pedagogical and psychological differences, intellectual and physical development of representatives of different social, class, ethnic, age and other groups.

"Differential education does not mean adapting the student to the didactic system, on the contrary, it means creating the necessary conditions for his comprehensive development and maturation as a person, taking into account his individual characteristics." This type of education should create the necessary conditions for students to develop themselves, gain independent knowledge, fully demonstrate their inner potential, abilities, physical training, and cognitive activity. Differentiated education serves to educate students such qualities as independence, initiative, responsibility, as well as independent, creative and critical thinking skills. In the organization of this education, pedagogues are required to approach each student as individually as possible, to respect his personality, to show confidence in him. Therefore, the participants of the differential education teaching process represent the need to create a favorable pedagogical environment for mutual learning and personal development in the form of pedagogue-student or student-student, student-student group, student-student team.

A pedagogue should strictly observe a number of conditions while using different types of education in physical culture training. These requirements include: being able to see each student as a separate, unique person; respect the student; ability to correctly assess the student's physical and mental condition; consideration of the student's wishes and interests; tolerant attitude to every student; confidence in the student's strength, potential and aspirations; create a comfortable learning environment for every student; create an opportunity for students to work independently or in small groups; teaching students to independently control their activities, to determine the effectiveness of their activities, to analyze the factors of success and the consequences of mistakes; - not to pressure any student during the educational process; not to

exaggerate the shortcomings of individual students; if a student's inability to master knowledge is noted, then without making a firm conclusion, to determine the reasons for this; - based on the determined reasons, to eliminate the student's inability to master knowledge without harming his honor and pride; to be able to create a "success environment" for each student in the educational process; to help every student succeed in their education; to develop the physical qualities of the student, to help him to follow a healthy lifestyle.

"During the process of differential education, the student will have the opportunity to develop a creative, critical approach to the learning material, to put forward new ideas, to justify them, to defend his opinion, to find an effective solution in problem situations." In order to form a fully mature and physically healthy person with a high culture, this process pays special attention to the education of the individual, the development of the physical capabilities of the person, and the acquisition of skills and knowledge in the field of physical culture and sports.

Thus, the issues of achieving the future professional development of learners, adapting them to social life based on the harmony of healthy thinking and beliefs are leading. Also, the issues of developing physical qualities of students with different physical development, developing healthy thinking and high moral qualities in experts with mature professional potential are gaining special relevance. The development of physical qualities of students in technical higher education institutions creates a foundation for the formation of strong will, healthy mind, sanogenic thinking and human qualities that will be necessary in their future activities.

REFERENCES

1. Davulov O.Q. Development of physical qualities in volleyball players on the basis of differential methods // *Akademika. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. India, October 10, 2020 Issue 10.
2. Davulov O.Q. Development of physical qualities of students in technical higher education institutions based on a differential approach // *Public education. Scientific-methodical magazine*. Tashkent, No. 6 of 2020. Page 85.
3. Davulov O.Q. Development of physical qualities of students based on differential methods // *Continuous education. Scientific methodological magazine*. Tashkent, 2021 special issue. Page 78.
4. Davulov O.Q. Development of physical qualities of students in technical higher education institutions based on differential methods // *Continuous education. Scientific methodological journal*. Tashkent, 2021, №4. B.-45-49.